

SECTION OF BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES

CONTOUR PLASTIC SURGERY AS AN INNOVATIVE METHOD OF NON-INVASIVE AESTHETIC CORRECTION

Nazarova Zh.

Kazakh scientific center of dermatology and infectious diseases

Abstract

This article examines innovative facial rejuvenation methods with a focus on contour plastic surgery as one of the most popular and effective approaches. The method involves the injection of biocompatible fillers, such as hyaluronic acid, to restore volume and improve facial contours. The versatility of contour plastic surgery is discussed, including its application for cheekbones, chin, and jawline correction. Special attention is given to modern injection techniques that minimize tissue trauma and reduce the risk of complications. Ethical aspects are highlighted, including facial harmony and the importance of setting realistic patient expectations. Contour plastic surgery is presented as a promising tool in aesthetic medicine.

Keywords: contour plastic surgery, hyaluronic acid, injection technologies, aesthetic correction, facial rejuvenation, cosmetology.

Introduction

Modern cosmetology has entered the era of technical and scientific novelties that offer patients a great variety of methods for preserving youth and improving appearance. Among the most sought-after procedures, facial contouring has gained popularity due to its effectiveness and safety. This technique not only copes with age-related changes but also allows for impressive aesthetic improvements without surgical intervention. Injection technologies using biocompatible fillers like hyaluronic acid, among others, form the very foundation of contour plastic surgery.

Contour plastic surgery is far from being just the correction of wrinkles. It is volumetric facial restoration, which includes the enhancement of the contours of the cheekbones, chin, and jawline. Besides, such procedures help to restore the lost volume, turning them into a universal tool for physicians in order to create a harmonious patient appearance individually.

Contour plastic surgery continues to evolve. Both the techniques of the administration of fillers and the materials themselves are in constant improvement, which helps to minimize risks and extend the duration of the effect. New technologies make the procedure not only safer but also minimally invasive, which significantly reduces the recovery time.

The purpose of this work is to discuss contour plastic surgery as one of the novel methods of aesthetic correction. The main characteristics of the procedure are analyzed: materials used, techniques, area of application, and the advantages and limitations of the method.

Main part. Principles of contour plastic surgery and injection techniques

Contour plastic surgery allows for facial feature modeling by restoring volume and improving skin texture. This procedure is based on the use of biocompatible materials that are injected into soft tissues to achieve aesthetic goals (table 1).

Table 1.

Characteristics of materials used in contour plastic surgery [1, 2]

Material	Composition	Key properties	Application
Hyaluronic acid	Natural polysaccharide	Binds water; hydrates and restores volume.	Correction of lips, nasolabial folds, cheekbones, and chin.
Collagen	Protein component of the dermis	Supports skin structure; stimulates regeneration.	Elimination of deep wrinkles; restoration of lost volume.
Poly lactic acid	Synthetic biodegradable material	Stimulates collagen production; provides long-term effect.	Correction of age-related changes; contour modeling.
Calcium hydroxyapatite	Mineral similar to bone tissue	Provides density and volume; stimulates collagen synthesis.	Tissue tightening, jawline and contour strengthening.
Polycaprolactone	Biocompatible polymer	Biodegrades in the body; promotes skin regeneration.	Long-term correction of deep wrinkles and fold.

Various techniques are used in contour plastic surgery for the administration of fillers. The traditional approach involves the use of fine needles. This method

allows for high precision in filler placement and is commonly employed for correcting smaller areas, such as

the lips and nasolabial folds. However, injection techniques with needles can cause microtraumas to the tissues, leading to temporary swelling and bruising.

Innovative approaches include the use of **cannulas** [3]. These flexible instruments have blunted tips,

therefore minimizing vascular and neural damage. Cannulas are indicated in the treatment of larger areas, among them the cheekbones, chin, and jawline. Their use minimizes bruising, reduces pain, and thus significantly improves the quality of the procedure as a whole (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Cannula and standard needle

Contour plastic surgery is used to correct various areas of the face. One of the most popular procedures is lip augmentation and shape modeling. This approach not only enhances volume but also addresses asymmetry. For the cheekbone area, contour plastic surgery is utilized to add definition and volume, providing a rejuvenated appearance. Chin correction helps improve the profile and harmonize facial proportions. Modifying the jawline shape creates more defined facial contours.

Each procedure is individualized, taking into consideration the particular characteristics of the patient. Contour plastic surgery requires a very good knowledge of facial anatomy and what the patient expects from the operation. It is thus highly individualized and concentrates on achieving harmony and naturalness. The type of material and technique used depends on specific aims, so the results will be long-lasting and aesthetically pleasing.

Development of technologies and improvement of materials

Modern technologies in contour plastics develop very fast, including the creation of new generations of fillers characterized by absolutely different properties. The material will have a high degree of biological inertness, providing extremely minimal chances for allergic reactions to the material. They create an effect of natural beauty without facial disharmonies. Developers place a strong emphasis on preserving the softness and flexibility of fillers, making the results more durable and aesthetically pleasing.

Modern fillers incorporate innovative components that enhance their effectiveness [4]. These formulations

include substances that stimulate the production of natural collagen and elastin. This improves skin texture and slows the aging process. Such materials not only enhance appearance but also have a positive effect on overall skin health by supporting its vitality.

One of the key directions in development is extending the longevity of fillers. Previously, most products maintained their effects for about six months. Today, the duration of results can reach two or even three years [5]. This has been achieved through advancements in material structures, allowing for slower resorption in tissues. Extending the duration reduces the need for repeated procedures, making them more convenient for patients.

Technological advancements are opening new horizons for plastic surgery. Advances of materials allow conducting the corrections in the most sparing way with least risk and at the top of effectiveness. Innovations noted above explain such growing popularity of the method among patients interested in their appearance and wishing to hold onto youth for a longer period of life.

Advantages of contour plastic surgery

Contour plastic surgery is one of the most effective and safe treatments in modern cosmetology. The method has become popular for patients who seek minimal intervention to improve their appearance. It is attractive because noticeable results can be achieved within a short period, with no need to spend extra time on rehabilitation. At the same time, contour plastics provide fewer traumatic options compared to surgical techniques while preserving high-quality natural-looking results (table 2).

Table 2.

Advantages of contour plastic surgery [6, 7]

Advantage	Description	Practical significance
Minimal invasive-ness	Fillers are administered through fine needles or canulas, eliminating the need for incisions or major interventions.	Reduced pain, lower risk of infection, and minimal tissue damage.
Short recovery period	Patients can return to normal activities within a few days after the procedure.	Convenient for individuals with busy schedules.
Possibility of gradual correction	The procedure allows for incremental adjustments in volume or contour improvement, tailored to individual needs.	Flexibility in achieving optimal results.
Long-lasting but reversible effect	Results last for 6 months to 2-3 years, after which the filler naturally dissolves.	Enables appearance updates without permanent changes.

Contour plastic surgery combines effectiveness, comfort, and high safety factor, making it one of the most popular methods of modern cosmetology. Low invasiveness of the procedure and short rehabilitation allow a wide range of patients to address this method, even those who avoid surgical interventions. The possibility of gradual correction allows for achieving optimal results while considering individual facial characteristics. Its long-lasting yet reversible effects create a balance between the durability of results and flexibility for future adjustments.

However, the success of the procedure also depends on ethical and aesthetic considerations. Maintaining facial proportions is crucial for achieving natural-looking results [8]. Overcorrection can lead to undesirable changes, which is why specialists must evaluate each case with professional caution. The responsibility of the practitioner involves not only technical execution but also managing patient expectations. Discussing the desired outcome, method limitations, and potential risks helps minimize dissatisfaction and prevent excessive corrections.

Thus, contour plastic surgery is not just a tool for addressing age-related changes but also a means to harmoniously highlight a patient's individuality. Ethics, aesthetics, and professional responsibility are key components in the successful application of this method.

Risks and limitations

Like any medical procedure, contour plastic surgery has a number of risks and limitations that should be considered while planning and performing it. Despite the high level of safety in modern methods and materials, possible complications are to be thoroughly paid attention to by both the practitioner and the patient.

Localised reactions are the most frequent complications, which include swelling, redness, and bruising at the sites of injection. These usually are temporary and may get resolved within a few days. However, it can also depict serious adverse effects in the form of allergic reactions to the filler. Symptoms of allergy may include itching, rashes, or serious swelling that requires immediate medical intervention.

Less common, but serious complications of facial fillers, include nodules, asymmetry, and migration of the filler. Poor injection technique or experience of the practitioner are the major reasons for these complications. Extra caution must be exerted whilst injecting fillers round large vessels, like in the nasolabial fold or around the eye. Incorrect placement of the filler into the

vessel can cause vascular occlusion, which is a medical emergency.

The practitioner's qualifications are very essential in mitigating risks. One has to have complete knowledge of facial anatomy, mastery of the method of injections, and rely on with the fabric for minimizing headaches. Further, the patient's fitness has to be analyzed through the practitioner for excluding systemic illnesses, predisposition to scar formation, or allergic reaction to one of the substances of fillers. Limitations of the method should also be acknowledged. Contour plastic surgery cannot fully replace surgical interventions in cases of severe age-related changes. The extent of correction achievable with injectable fillers is limited. Patients with significant structural changes in soft tissues or facial deformities may not achieve satisfactory results and might require a comprehensive approach, including surgical options.

In short, the risks and limitations of contour plastic surgery require detailed pre-procedure analysis and preparation. The basic responsibility of the practitioner in selecting materials and techniques, as well as evaluating the condition of the patient, is incumbent upon him for the successful outcome and minimizing complications. Informing the patient about potential risks and setting realistic expectations are equally vital in ensuring satisfactory results.

Conclusion

Contour plastic surgery is the new word in aesthetic correction, which amazingly combines the highest efficiency, safety, and minimally invasive methods. Biocompatible materials used, such as hyaluronic acid and polylactic acid, ensure natural-looking and durable results. Modern advancements in materials and technologies enhance the longevity of effects and broaden the method's applications. This could mean a personalized approach, one that considers facial anatomy and the patient's aesthetic preference, and makes contour plastic surgery versatile to both improve facial features and address age-related changes.

Contour plastic surgery should be performed by a highly qualified specialist, who is responsible for selecting the material and method of injection, and keeping the facial proportions. Such a minimally invasive type of surgery has some risks: allergic reactions, swelling, and other complications, which indicates a strict following of the medical prescriptions. Ethical considerations, including managing patient expecta-

tions and avoidance of overcorrection, are very important in such aesthetic and safe surgeries. In the future, the developments in contour plastic surgery such as material improvement, minimizing risks, and new technologies will reinforce its position among the most leading methods in modern aesthetic medicine.

References

1. Su D. et al. Clinical applications of a novel poly-L-lactic acid microsphere and hyaluronic acid suspension for facial depression filling and rejuvenation //Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology. – 2024.
2. Cruel P. T. E. et al. Calcium Hydroxyapatite in Its Different Forms in Skin Tissue Repair: A Literature Review //Surgeries. – 2024. – V. 5. – №. 3. – P. 640-659.
3. Al-Hage J., MD H. I. G. The Needle Versus Cannula //Hot Topics in Cosmetic Dermatology, An Issue of Dermatologic Clinics, E-Book: Hot Topics in Cosmetic Dermatology, An Issue of Dermatologic Clinics, E-Book. – 2023. – V. 42. – №. 1. – P. 69-77.
4. Tettamanzi M. et al. Advancements in face and neck contouring: integrating radiofrequency-assisted liposuction with FaceTite and buccal fat pad excision for facial slimming //Aesthetic Plastic Surgery. – 2024. – P. 1-8.
5. Choi J., Yi K. H. Using multiple wavelengths in order to improve the facial contouring procedure by the lipolysis and sculpting //Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology. – 2024. – V. 23. – №. 2. – P. 464-469.
6. Tettamanzi M. et al. Advancements in face and neck contouring: integrating radiofrequency-assisted liposuction with FaceTite and buccal fat pad excision for facial slimming //Aesthetic Plastic Surgery. – 2024. – P. 1-8.
7. Tettamanzi M. et al. Advancements in face and neck contouring: integrating radiofrequency-assisted liposuction with FaceTite and buccal fat pad excision for facial slimming //Aesthetic Plastic Surgery. – 2024. – P. 1-8.
8. Braz A., de Paula Eduardo C. C. The facial shapes in planning the treatment with injectable fillers //Indian Journal of Plastic Surgery. – 2020. – V. 53. – №. 02. – P. 230-243.